

THE STUDY OF REDOX REACTIONS IN CHEMISTRY USING INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: *In this article analyzes the teaching of redox reactions in chemistry using information technology. The importance of software applications, mobile applications, virtual laboratories, which are part of information technology in science teaching, was also discussed.*

Keywords: *chemistry, oxidation, reduction, reaction, information technology, software, application, virtual laboratory*

Chemistry is often referred to as a central science, because it combines physics and mathematics, biology and medicine, and earth and environmental sciences. Therefore, knowledge about the nature of chemicals and chemical processes provides insight into various physical and biological phenomena.

Combustion is the first point of philosophical and scientific attention among the chemical processes currently considered in chemistry as oxidation-reduction reactions. The Greek philosopher Empedocles emphasized fire as one of the four elements of matter. Nowadays, the Phlogiston theory is scientifically popular. This theory was first proposed by the German chemist G. E. Stahl in 1697, who stated that during the burning process of matter, the elemental component - phlogiston is released. Thus, coal burning was interpreted as the loss of phlogiston from carbon to air. The theory was also applied to processes other than combustion: in the extraction of metal from its oxide by heating with coal, for example, phlogiston was thought to have changed from carbon to oxide.

As we study and analyze the history of oxidation-reduction in chemistry, oxidation is the process by which one atom removes electrons from another and claims them for itself. This is one aspect of redox-type reactions. These oxidation-reduction reactions differ from other types of chemical interactions because they involve changes in the electron shells of several atoms. Reduction is the process by which one atom transfers electrons to another.

The term derives its name from oxygen, as it was considered the first known oxidizing element. In fact, for a good while in the 18th century, "oxidation" was simply about adding oxygen to a compound. A good example of this traditional definition for oxidation can manifest itself in the body of our cars: rust (iron oxide). In this process, we learn that oxidation is not limited to iron or oxygen. Many elements can be oxidized in a variety of environments with proper co-oxidation.

A redox reaction is a type of chemical reaction that involves the transfer of electrons between two species. A redox reaction is any chemical reaction in which the oxidation number of a molecule, atom, or ion changes by gaining or losing electrons. Redox reactions are common and vital to some of the basic functions of life, including photosynthesis, respiration, combustion, corrosion, or rusting.

It should be noted that the degree of oxidation is the formal (conditional) charge of an element in this compound, if it is assumed that the compound has a completely ionic structure.

P0 P-3 P+5 P+3

e=15 e=18 e=10 e=12

p=15 p=15 p=15 p=15

The oxidation state of an element corresponds to the number of electrons, i.e. e-, that an atom loses, gains, or uses when combined with other atoms in compounds. When determining the oxidation state of an atom, the following should be followed:

- Oxidation level of atoms or simple substances in free state is equal to 0.

- Total oxidation state of all atoms: equal to 0 in neutral species and equal to ionic charge in ion.

- Oxidation level of metals of group 1 is +1, oxidation level of group 2 is +2

The oxidation state of fluorine in compounds is -1

- Hydrogen usually has +1 oxidation state in compounds

- Oxygen usually has an oxidation state of -2 in compounds

- In binary metal compounds, group 17 elements have an oxidation state of -1, group 16 elements -2, and group 15 elements -3.

- H+1, H-1 (in metal hydrides), O-2, O-1, O+1, O+2 (F₂O), O+1 (F₂O₂), F-

- the degree of oxidation can be -, 0, +, fractional numbers.

16- When the sign changes from top to bottom, the oxidizer is reversed

When the sign changes from low to high, the reducing agent is oxidized

Reactions with a change in the oxidation state of elements are called oxidation-reduction reactions.

Oxidation process - the degree of oxidation increases in the process of giving electrons to an atom, molecule, ion, the particle in it is called a reducing agent and is oxidized.

- $E^0 - ne \rightarrow E^{+n}$

- E⁰ is a reductant

- n - the number of given electrons

- e is an electron

- reduction process - the process of electron attachment of particles, in which the particle is called an oxidant, the degree of oxidation is reduced and returned.

- $E^0 + ne \rightarrow E^{-n}$

- E⁰ - oxidizer

- n - the number of electrons received

- e is an electron

oxidizing only both oxidizing and reducing only reducing only

N+5, P+5, S+6, O-2, Fe+3, Na+, Ca+2, anode N0, N+1, N+2, N+3, N+4, S0, S+4 ,
Mn+2, Mn+4 N-3, P-3, Mn0, Na0, Ca0, S-2, O-2, cathode

Teaching oxidation-reduction reactions in chemistry with the help of information technology is one of the most important topics. Nowadays, various methods, methods, technologies and teaching tools are used in education to provide knowledge to the learner.

Passing the lessons through presentation has given effective results in theory, but its application in practice is the foundation stone for acquiring deep knowledge. Today is the age of technology, and a student who learns processes in chemistry can not only master them in the course of the lesson, but also perform them independently at home.

Can acquire chemical knowledge. We can see this in the example of computer or mobile device applications:

This software application is called "Redox Reaction - Chemistry" through this application, students will observe the process of redox reactions by visualizing colorful images and videos and learn to balance redox reactions in an easy and fun way, and it is a useful interactive application.

Studying chemical reactions is the main part of chemistry process, apart from this above program, another useful mobile application called "chemical reactions" is also giving effective, positive results in studying chemical reactions.

Reaction equation $2Li + Br_2 = 2LiBr$ Conditions $t > 200^\circ C$ Continuation and balancing of the chemical reaction

Reaction equation $2Li + 2C = Li_2C_2$ Conditions $t > 200^\circ C$, aq. and T

The reaction equation is $2Li + 2CH_3COOH = 2LiCH_3COO + H_2$

Reaction equation $2Li + Cl_2 = 2LiCl$ Conditions $t > 200^\circ C$

In addition, it is possible to solve examples in class and analyze their answers by gaining deeper knowledge of the subject through various websites, online and offline programs.

Also, the use of virtual laboratories is widely used in the teaching process.

Advantages of using virtual laboratories in education:

- Virtual use of high-end equipment
- Serve as a visual guide for teaching complex concepts
- Ensuring the safety of students
- Engaging students in science
- Offer instant feedback
- Ensure flexibility of learning
- An affordable alternative to physical laboratories

In conclusion, the teaching of oxidation-reduction reactions in chemistry with the help of information technology serves as the main tool for acquiring the concepts, processes, and practical experiences necessary for students in chemistry education, and for students to express their opinions. positively enables its formation.

References

1. Tursunov S.Q. Ta'limda elektron axborot resurslarini yaratish va ularni joriy qilishning metodik asoslari: Avtoref.dis.. ped.fan.nomzodi. Toshkent. 2011. - 24b.
2. Zaylobov L.T, Rahmatullaev N.G, Toshpo'latov Y.T. Kimyoni o'qitishda axborot texnologiyasidan foydalanish. XVIII. ULUSAL KIMYA kongresi, Turkiya, Kars 2004, 741. - 1209 b.
3. Petrucci, et al. General Chemistry: Principles & Modern Applications. 9th ed. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson/Prentice Hall, 2007.
4. Sadava, et al. Life: The Science of Biology. 8th ed. New York, NY. W.H. Freeman and Company, 2007
5. Yermesha Kyle; Stephen Bacon; Amber Park; Jameka Griffin; Raicherylon Cummins; Raymond Hooks, Bailu Qian and Hua-Jun Fan, "Teaching Chemistry Effectively with Engineering Majors: Teaching Beyond the Textbook", Chemical Education and Sustainability in the Global Age, Proceedings of 21st ICCE. (Editor: Mei-Hung Chiu), Springer. (2011)

6. Public Perceptions of Chemistry, Qualitative Research, Management Report
(Royal Society of Chemistry, 1995)